

Plasma Treated PET Nanofiber Veils: A Novel Interface Enhancement for Cryogenic Composite Applications

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Research Background

Conventional Autoclave Manufacturing for High Pressure

- Composites are typically manufactured using autoclaves, which apply **heat** and **pressure** to cure the material and produce a **void-free structure**.
- However, autoclaves have several **limitations**, including **high energy consumption**, **large space requirements**, and their tendency to become a **bottleneck** in the production process [1].

<Void Content Difference Between VBO and Autoclave>

<Autoclave for Boeing 777X Composite Wings [2]>

Effect of Voids on Mechanical Properties

- **Minimizing voids** is critical, as voids significantly degrade the mechanical properties of the final product.
- Therefore, there is a **need for Out-of-Autoclave (OoA)** manufacturing processes that can ensure **void-free composites**.

<Void Content and the Change in Short Beam Shear Strength [3]>

<Void Content and the Change in Interlaminar Shear Strength [4]>

Use of Nano-Porous Networks – Alternative to Autoclaves

- One solution is to **interleave nanoporous networks** within the composite prior to curing, allowing them to conform to and fill the rough interfaces between adjacent prepreg layers [5].
- Additionally, these nanoporous networks generate **capillary pressure** during curing, which can partially **substitute** external pressure provided by an autoclave [6].
- Furthermore, the nanoporous networks can **enhance toughness** by acting as a **buffer** for coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) mismatches, which arise from the differing orientations of prepreg plies [7].

<Schematic of Composite Curing w/ & w/o Nano-Porous Networks [5]>

Microcracks

Delamination

<Microcracks and Delamination Caused by CTE Mismatch [8]>

Candidates for Nano-Porous Network - Polymers

- Engineering polymers are promising candidates for nanoporous networks due to their **high strain capacity** and **toughness**, making them effective CTE buffers.
- **Polyamide (PA)** -based composite reinforcements—such as XLB from Nanolayr—are already **commercially available**.
- However, some high-toughness engineering polymers, including PEEK, HDPE, and UHMWPE, **cannot be easily fabricated into nanostructured forms** [9,10].

Material	Modulus (Gpa)	Tensile strength (Mpa)
Polyethylene (PE)	0.88	35
Polyurethane (PU)	0.02	35
Polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE)	0.5	27.5
Polyacetal (PA)	2.1	67
Polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA)	2.55	59
Polyethylene terephthalate (PET)	2.85	61
Polyether ketone (PEEK)	8.3	139
Silicone rubber (SR)	0.008	7.6
Polysulfone (PS)	2.65	75

<Mechanical Properties of Engineering Polymers [11]>

<PA Composite Reinforcement (Nanolayr XLB)>

Importance of Cryogenic Properties in Aerospace Composites

- **Mechanical performance at cryogenic temperatures** is critical, particularly with the growing use of cryogenic fuels and composite overwrapped pressure vessels (COPVs).
- However, **PA exhibit poor mechanical properties under cryogenic conditions**, limiting their applicability in such environments.

<Composite Overwrapped Pressure Vessel [12, 13]>

<Mechanical Properties of PA [14] & PET [15] at -196 °C>

Limitation of PET – Poor Adhesion with Composites

- PET exhibits **poor adhesion to epoxy**, which limits its effectiveness as a reinforcing material in composites [16].
- Composites interleaved with PET veils demonstrated **no significant improvement in toughness** [17].

❖ This study focuses on **plasma treatment** to enhance PET's adhesion to epoxy, enabling its use as a **nanofiber reinforcement** and potentially improving **cryogenic toughness**.

<Mode I Test Schematic & Results for PA & PET Interleaved Composites [16]>

Material & Methods

Synthesizing Nanofibers - Electrospinning

- Electrospinning is a technique that uses a high-voltage electric field to draw a polymer solution into fine fibers, which solidify as they reach a grounded collector [18].
- This enables the fabrication of **nanoscale fibers**, offering enhanced mechanical properties across a range of polymers [18].
- Fiber diameter is controlled by **adjusting key process parameters** such as voltage, flow rate, and solution concentration [19].
- 1 hour of electrospinning produced 4.5 gsm of PET nanofiber, with thickness of 60 μm .

<Electrospinning Machine>

<SEM Image of Electrospun PET Nanofibers (Top & Side view)>

<Distribution of Nanofiber Diameters>

Plasma Treatment for Improving PET Adhesion

- Atmospheric plasma processing offers several advantages over conventional low-pressure systems: **high throughput**, **simpler equipment**, and **no need for vacuum chambers or special gases**, which increases **industrial applicability**.
- Plasma treatment has been widely used to enhance polymer surface adhesion [20,21], but this study is the **first to apply atmospheric plasma to nanofibers**.

<Atmospheric Plasma Generator & Schematic of Plasma Treatment>

Use of Metal Mesh to Prevent Shedding of Nanofibers

- High air pressure (6 bar) generated by atmospheric plasma can **dislodge nanofibers**, reducing their effectiveness.
- A **metal mesh** support (60 & 2500) enables **closer** and **longer plasma exposure** while preventing nanofiber shedding.
- With a 1 cm nozzle-to-sample distance, both mesh prevented nanofiber shedding, while achieving comparable plasma treatment efficiency.

<Shedding of Nanofibers due to Plasma Treatment>

<Use of 60 Mesh & 2500 Mesh to Prevent Shedding>

<Plasma Treatment Pattern>

<PET Nanofibers Transferred to Composites after Plasma Treatment>

Composite Curing Process with Interleaved Nanofibers

- After plasma treatment, PET nanofibers are **interleaved between each lamina** during the prepreg layup process.
- Laminates are then cured by **Vacuum-Bag-Only (VBO)** method, following the cure cycle for IM7/8552 (autoclave required).
- Three sample types were prepared: baseline (no interleaved nanofibers), As-spun PET, and Plasma-treated PET.

<Composite Laminate Interleaved with PET Nanofibers>

<Schematic of Composite Curing Setup>

<Vacuum-Bag-Only>

<Cure Cycle>

<Composite Laminates after Cure>

Results & Discussion

Morphological & Chemical
Composition Change
after Plasma Treatment

PET Nanofiber Morphology Retention after Plasma Treatment

- Despite **6 bar of air pressure** and **120 °C plasma temperature** involved in plasma treatment, SEM analysis confirms that **nanofiber structure does not have distinctive change**.
- The use of a metal mesh enables effective plasma exposure while preserving the **integrity of the nanofibers**.
- These findings indicate that even after plasma treatment, PET nanofibers can act as **nanoporous networks** that help **eliminate voids** in composite materials.

<SEM Images of Electrospun PET Nanofibers Before & After Atmospheric Plasma Treatment>

Surface Energy Increase via Plasma (Contact Angle Analysis)

- Contact angle analyzer was used to assess change in the wettability of PET nanofibers.
- Reduced contact angle with deionized water indicates **increased hydrophilicity**, confirming a **rise in surface energy**.
- Consistent with previous studies on PET films, plasma treatment enhances the hydrophilicity of PET nanofibers, demonstrating its **effectiveness even in nanostructures**.
- For more detailed and quantitative analysis on increased hydrophilicity, X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS) was conducted.

Before Treatment:
120° with DI water

Plasma
Treatment
➔

After Treatment:
30° with DI water

<Contact Angle Difference Before & After Plasma Treatment>

Surface Energy Increase via Plasma (XPS Analysis)

- Atomic composition showed a 15% decrease in carbon content and a 12% increase in oxygen content.
- High-resolution C-scan revealed **40% reduction in phenyl (C–C, C=C) bonds**, while O-scan showed a **45% increase** in organic C=O and a **61.5% increase** in C–O bonds, explaining the **enhanced hydrophilicity and increased surface energy**.
- These indicate a **potential enhancement in adhesion to epoxy**, which will be assessed through Short Beam Shear (SBS).

Optical Microscope Image of PET Interleaved Composites

- Void content were analyzed using **IM7/8552 prepregs** (Hexcel) with $[45/0/-45/90]_{2s}$ layup cured with **VBO method**.
- Void content of 1.6% present in the baseline samples were **eliminated** in both PET-interleaved composites.
- Plasma-treated PET nanofibers **generate sufficient capillary pressure** confirming the conservation of nanofibers.
- The thickness of each interleaved PET nanofibers was 12 ~ 15 μm , while overall composite thickness for PET interleaved composites increased by 60 ~ 100 μm compared to baseline.

<Baseline Composite>

<As-Spun PET Composite>

<Plasma PET Composite>

Short Beam Shear (SBS) Tests
for Analyzing the Toughening Effect
of PET Nanofibers

Short Beam Shear (SBS) Test Setup – ASTM D2344

- To evaluate the reinforcing effect of plasma-treated PET, SBS tests were conducted on three types of composites: **Baseline**, **As-spun PET**, and **Plasma-treated PET**.
- SBS tests were performed in accordance with **ASTM D2344**, using **IM7/8552** prepregs (Hexcel).
- **[45/0/-45/90]_{2S}** layup configuration was employed, and samples were fabricated using **both VBO and autoclave processes**.
- This layup structure **enables comparison with reference data** from the National Center for Advanced Materials Performance (**NCAMP**).

<Schematic of SBS>

<VBO Curing>

<Autoclave Curing>

<Manufacturer Recommended Cure Cycle for IM7/8552>

Short Beam Shear (SBS) Result Comparison

- Plasma-treated PET composites exhibited **improved Short Beam Strength** compared to their respective baselines.
- Although the SBS value of Plasma PET (VBO) was lower than that of the Baseline (Autoclave) sample, this difference is likely attributed to **variations in specimen thickness**.

<Short Beam Strength Comparison>

<Thickness Comparison>

Short Beam Shear (SBS) – Load v. Displacement

- Furthermore, load v. displacement curve shows **no significant difference in maximum load** between the Baseline (Autoclave) and Plasma PET (VBO) specimens.
- While both show similar maximum load, Short Beam Strength of the VBO specimen appear lower due to its greater thickness.

<Short Beam Strength Comparison>

<Load v. Displacement Curve>

Short Beam Shear (SBS) – Load v. Displacement

- In contrast, **both As-spun PET** specimen showed Short Beam Strength values **comparable to Baseline (VBO)**.
- **Low adhesion of PET** did not contribute to composite reinforcement and may have **behaved similarly to voids**.
- Additionally, comparison with NCAMP* reference values confirmed that the Short Beam Strength value of the Baseline (Autoclave) specimen closely matched the standard, **validating the reliability of the experimental results**.

<Short Beam Strength Comparison>

<Load v. Displacement Curve>

SBS Result Comparison – Crack Analysis (VBO)

- Optical microscopy revealed that Plasma-treated PET composites exhibited more frequent occurrences of “ply-jumps” compared to untreated PET composites.
- The increased number of ply-jumps suggests **composite reinforcement** [22], showing successful adhesion increase due to plasma treatment.
- Also, the higher surface area created from the crack indicates a higher energy flux [23], indicating toughening of plasma treated PET nanofibers compared to As-spun PET nanofibers.

<As-Spun PET interleaved Composites after SBS>

<Plasma Treated PET interleaved Composites after SBS>

SBS Result Comparison – Crack Analysis (Autoclave)

- **Similar increases in ply-jump frequency** were observed in Baseline (Autoclave) and Plasma-treated PET (Autoclave), whereas As-spun PET—even when processed via autoclave—showed no ply-jump formation.
- These results, along with SBS values, confirm the **reinforcing effect** of plasma-treated PET in composites.
- Furthermore, the observed intralaminar failure suggests that plasma-treated PET nanofibers enhance composite toughness not only by eliminating voids but also by **directly strengthening the interlaminar region**.

<Baseline Composites after SBS>

<As-Spun PET Interleaved Composites after SBS>

<Plasma Treated PET interleaved Composites after SBS>

SBS Result Comparison – Crack Analysis (VBO, SEM)

- To perform a more detailed analysis of the fracture surfaces, the interlaminar regions of VBO composites containing As-spun PET and Plasma Treated PET were examined using SEM, both before and after SBS testing.
- In composites with As-spun PET, the fracture path propagated linearly through the interlaminar region.
- In contrast, composites with plasma-treated PET exhibited a more complex fracture path, propagating through both interlaminar and intralaminar regions, **indicating increased adhesion** from non-linear, more tortuous fracture behavior.

<PET Nanofiber Region Before SBS>

<As-Spun PET Composites after SBS>

<Plasma Treated PET interleaved Composites after SBS>

Conclusion & Future Work

Conclusion

➤ This research has:

1. Developed an **atmospheric plasma treatment** method that **functionalizes nanofibers while retaining its morphology**, **enabling previously unused materials as nanoporous networks** for void elimination with **high industrial applicability**.
2. Shown that plasma-treated PET nanofibers markedly increase short beam shear strength, **overcoming their adhesion with epoxy**, and **reinforcing composites**.

<Retention of Nanofibers after Plasma Treatment>

<Increased Short Beam Shear Strength with Plasma PET>

Future Work – Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA)

- Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA) in **dual-cantilever mode** will be conducted to evaluate composite modulus.
- Temperature sweep from $-100\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $300\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ compared the **low-temperature modulus and glass-transition temperature (T_g)** of baseline, PET-interleaved laminates, and **PA-interleaved laminate** (Xantulayr, XLB) will be added for comparison.
- DMA measurements will be repeated after liquid-nitrogen cryogenic cycles to assess modulus retention.
- **$[0/90]_{4s}$** layup with IM7/8552 prepreg is chosen to maximize coefficient-of-thermal-expansion mismatch during cycling.

<DMA 850 (TA) – Dual Cantilever>

<Cryogenic Cycle>

Future Work – Permeability Measurements

- Higher **post-cycling storage modulus** of PET-interleaved laminates compared to baseline laminates demonstrates their **suitability for reusable space-launch structures**.
- Future work will focus on **permeability tests of PET interleaved composites** for use in **Type V composite overwrapped pressure vessel (COPV)**, focusing on **low hydrogen permeability of PET** while being **capable of multiple use**.

<Hydrogen Permeability for Different Thermoplastic Materials [25]>

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